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THE ROLE OF TEXT ANALYTICAL COMPETENCE IN TRANSLATOR TRAINING AND EDUCATION

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Abstract

There is a lot of ongoing debate as to whether translators should spend time trying to analyze a source text before translating it or just go ahead with its translation once the source text is readable. The goal of this study is to assess the role of text analytical competence in translation performance. An evaluation of the text analytical mastery of 50 advanced students in translation in Advanced School of Translators and Interpreters (ASTI) was conducted in order to raise awareness of the actual source text comprehension challenges facing trainee translators. The study posits that text analytical competence contributes significantly to translation achievement and poor performances in translation largely result from poor or inadequate understanding of the text to be translated. The empirical study takes the form of a protocol test of a 300 words translation into English administered to 50 advanced students of the ASTI, University of Buea in Cameroon. The results demonstrate that professional translation is not a simple substitution of terminology and some basic knowledge of grammar. Professional translation involves analyzing the situation and function of the text in relation to the focus of its translation. These specific characteristics of the translation process are what determine the type of text analytical competence required for producing optimal translations. The study proposes a text analytical course program that is tailored to respond to these new professional profiles of the translator.

Keywords:

Translation, Source text, Text analysis, Competence, Effective Translation, curriculum design.

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1. Introduction

Waddington (2000: 2) defines ‘translation competence’ as “a combination of linguistic competence and the ability to translate.” In spite of this obvious symbiotic relationship, language competence, especially reading comprehension or text analytical competence is one of those unfortunate indispensable sub-components of translation competence that has been downplayed unjustifiably. Poor or inadequate mastery of the working languages would cause difficulties in understanding the message in the source text or even worse so, on how to communicate it in the target language. As, Selmla (2008: 132) rightly intimates:

No language can exist unless it is steeped in the context of culture, and no culture can exist which does not have at its center, the structure of natural language. Language, then, is the heart within the body of culture, and it is the interaction between the two that results in the continuation of life-energy

However, translators need to be more than just competent in their working languages and cultures to be able to produce quality translations. Competences such as transfer competence, communicative competence, digital competence, and especially text analytical competence, etc. are considered to be prerequisites for effective translation in this study.

Can trainee translators produce acceptable translations by being competent in text analysis? Can this step of translation be skipped and still end up with a good translation? There is a lot of ongoing debate as to whether translators should spend time trying to analyze a source text before translating, or just go ahead with translation once the source text is readable. To what extent does text analytical competence influence the quality of translations? What specific text analytical strategies and methods do translation students use when translating? What pedagogical approaches can be used to develop textual analytical competence in trainee translators?

The purpose of this study is to highlight the important role played by text analytical competence in the production of quality translations. It demonstrates that source text analysis is very essential in achieving the goal of translation, because the translator has to understand the source text in order to translate better in the target language.

2. Literature Review

Even though reading competence is of great importance for formal and informal education, studies show that the students do not always succeed in adequately developing this

vital competence (Mičić, 2020). Although there are many competences that contribute to translation performance, this study focuses on text analytical competence and the role it plays in determining the outcome of translation performance. The way translation is approached has changed, not only because of the influence of new translation approaches that have informed translator training but also because source texts have changed, too (Dicerto, 2018: 15)

Text analytical competence is discussed using insights from the literature on translation competence studies and on the competency-based approaches to translator training. Within this theoretical framework, the concept of text analytical competence is deconstructed into reading comprehension language skills or ‘enhanced translational language skills.’, which offer new ways of teaching and learning that critically engage students in rich learning environments for skills development and professionalization in Translator Training and Education.

To produce good translations, knowledge of the communication function and its place in a particular contextual situation is important. Hence, it is important to analyze the situation and function of the text with regards to the focus and objective of the translation. Popelkova (2017: 415) highlights that “it would be a mistake to believe that in professional translation a simple substitution of terminology and a very basic knowledge of grammar would suffice” to create a quality target text. He emphasizes on the importance of an extensive understanding of the text to be translated. This can only be achieved through a well-studied text analytical approach.

2.1 The Concept of Text Analytical Competence

The German philosopher Schleiermacher (1999) opines that translation, as a process is always associated with comprehension, reasoning and transfer (communication). He lays emphasis on comprehension due to its most prominent ties with translation. From this definition, translation is an act of perception, inasmuch as the key objective of translation effort lies in making the source text understandable to the reader. All source text features such as form and content, its goals and communicative functions, as well as its aesthetic value are shaped based on a broad spectrum of concurrent factors that define the author’s choices in the process of text generation.

In its simplest form Text Analysis refers to the process of systematically examining and interpreting text data to uncover meaningful information. This method involves utilizing computational and linguistic technique to dissect text and extract relevant insights. By breaking won text content into its constituent parts, Text Analysis helps to discover valuable patterns, associations and trends that would otherwise remain hidden,

A text is any stretch of language that can be understood in context. In this vein, Translation is understood as an act of carrying the meaning of a text from one language to another. This process involves interpretation of meaning of the source text and producing the same meaning in another language. Text however cannot exist out of context. By context what is meant is the entire environment in which the word or sentence is expressed or stated. So, a translator has to go into the background of the text to understand the text.

Context is also at the core of discourse analysis, since all interaction involves context. In order to understand, speakers must rely on context and their linguistic choices are motivated by contextual factors such as topic, participants place, time etc.

2.2 The Translator's Linguistic knowledge-base.

The increasing need for trainees' language boosting has remained a perennial problem in translator training in general. According to Sakwe (2013), the problem of language development has frequently been disregarded, tacitly assuming the existence of perfect bilingual trainee translators. And he adds:

Reports from all over the world testify to the existence of language problems among trainee translators, even where these languages are natively spoken (cf. Li 2001, Laszlo 2000b, Almborg 1997, Cao 1996, Neubert 1995, Kussmaul 1995, Pym 1992) etc. This calls for the need to validate the knowledge base brought to the classroom by the students (Sakwe, 2013: 51)

The duty of the translator is to unlock the prison of language and to help a text break free of its limited original language, culture, and audience. The translator must be able to (1) read and comprehend the source language and (2) write comprehensibly in the target language. The translator must also be able to (3) choose the equivalent expression in the target language that both fully conveys and best matches the meaning intended in the source language (referred to as congruity judgment). This points to how wide and how subtle the translator's linguistic knowledge should be.

Margaret F Lang (in Snell-Hornsby 1992: 395) affirms that there is a growing problem of mother tongue competence and that this is slowly being recognized by teachers in several disciplines and especially teachers of translation. Because of its importance for any translation performance, the mother tongue or ‘A’ language should be further developed and refined in the course of the curriculum by means of specific practice activities.

Translation also requires a highly developed capacity to understand the ‘B’ language of the source text. Hatim and Mason (1990: 6) explain the difficulty of the understanding process: “(...) it is erroneous to assume that the meaning of a text is composed of the sum of the meaning of the individual lexical items so that any attempt to translate at this level is bound to miss important elements of meaning.” In other words, in the study of language, one should take into account a good number of social, cultural, and situational factors that are assumed to affect language use and its features.

Lastly, it would be unacceptable to talk about linguistic competence without pointing at the vital necessity of communicative competence. Hatim and Mason (1990: 33) opine that “the translator’s communicative competence is attuned to what is communicatively appropriate in both SL and TL communities and individual acts of translation may be evaluated in terms of their appropriateness to the context of their use. Mansouri (2005: 20) has stressed:

Precise knowledge of the limits of appropriateness in each language (communicative competence), mastery of textual features and effective writing devices, awareness of where differences and where similarities lie...is extremely important to translate safely, without distorting the specificity of any language.

2.3 Translation Competence

There are common words that arise across the literature like “competence”, “competency” and “competent”, each of which has a unique definition and application. According to Hager & Gonczi, (1996), competency is the capability to choose and use (apply) an integrated combination of knowledge, skills and attitudes with the intention to realize a task in a certain context in which characteristics such as motivation, self-confidence, and willpower are incorporated. On the other hand, competence is defined as the capacity to accomplish ‘up to standard’ the key occupational tasks that characterize a profession.

The competences required by a profession are usually determined by studying the behaviour and actions of the field’s successful professionals. In this vein, educating new

professionals should ideally be a reflection of the everyday practice of the field, and students are expected to be taught how to function in the professional arena.

Competence-based Education (CBE) is described as a paradigm shift from ‘classical education’. Significant developments in society in the past decades have led to different views about knowledge, accompanied by an increase of attention on the acquisition of competencies and competence-based education and training (Kearns, 2001). CBE appeals to institutions for a variety of reasons, including Employability, Accountability, Affordability, and Accessibility. As Gibbons (1998) rightly points out, the acquisition of knowledge for its own sake is no longer the major aim of education and training, but the application of the acquired knowledge.

In contrast to a long experience and background in other countries, competence-based initiatives in Cameroon are at the early stages of development. In Cameroon, the BMP and CBA paradigms were integrated in the university system following two ministerial texts: ministerial decision n° 06/0321/MINESUP/CAB/IGA/CJ of 16th May, 2006 set the framework for the implementation of the BMP, and this was accompanied by the ministerial circular n°07/0003/MINESUP/CAB/IGA of 19th October, 2007, which spelt out the general modalities relating to the framework of the BMP system in higher education. According to the above circular:

La finalité du système LMD est tour à tour: le développement par la contribution à la croissance de l'économie nationale et à la promotion de l'emploi de ses diplômés; le développement social, culturel et humain par la formation d'une nouvelle génération de cadres dotés d'une solide formation citoyenne et aptes à répondre aux défis du millénaire...[the two alternative aims of the BMP system are to contribute to the country's economic growth and graduate employment; to foster socio-cultural and human capital development through the training of a new generation of top executives endowed with a strong moral base and prepared to face today's challenges] (My translation)

Models depicting the ‘ideal’ translator are based on the various skills and personality traits possessed by successful professionals in the field of translation. This view highlights the importance of translation competence as the goal that is pursued in the teaching-learning process. However, the development of models of translation competence is still in its infancy (Göpferich, 2011).

Although this work is focused on text analytical competence, it is worth noting that there are other competences which translators must have. They include: Linguistic

competence, cultural competence, Transfer competence, Extralinguistic competence, Professional competence and Digital competence etc. Among the 13 models of competence cited in the literature, the following 8 models of Jean Delisle (1980), Christian Nord (1988), Amparo Hurtado (1996), Hatim and Mason (1997), Albrecht Neubert (2000), Schaffner and Beverly (2000), Dorothy Kelly (2007), Stuart Campbell (2008) evoke textual analysis or text reception or text comprehension (used interchangeably) as one of the translation sub-competences. A translation competency framework is a model that broadly defines the blueprint for 'excellent' performance within the profession. *The European Master in Translation (EMT) Framework* and *Tuning Competence-based Learning* are good examples of frameworks of international repute in translation.

2.4 Text Analytical Competence

Text analysis can simply be defined as the process of studying a text in order to understand the author's deliberate meaning. This generally involves finding answers for the what, who, where, when, why and for whom questions. Text analysis involves analyzing the internal and external factors of a source text. The purpose of textual analysis is to describe the content, structure, and functions of the messages contained in texts. In the translation process, the translator has to make divisions at various levels, either textual, language or ethical ones. However, translators can arrive at proper decisions if they have the relevant information at their disposal. Hence, the need to always discuss translation details with the client. This involves knowing the questions to ask the client in order to be able to produce the target text that will match the client's requirements. Each text created by the author carries some communication intent and is designed for a particular target.

The process of understanding a text cannot be reduced to its external characteristics, part of the understanding is also the specific situation in which the text originates. Also, the understanding process involves source text culture in which the author lives, which is found in the text (implicitly or explicitly), and the target text culture given that in order for a translation to fulfill the role for which it is intended, the text has to be understood by the target group. In the process, the translator identifies defect elements in the source text. All this would lead to effective translation. Nevertheless, the other components of the translation process (preliminary text analysis or draft translation) are not quite clearly defined in their overall task of achieving high-quality translation.

A translator will not only need this to be able to interact with a source text. We are also concerned with his mental representation of the source text as a language event found in a certain culture and produced in accordance with certain asocio-cultural convention. According to Wilss (1982: 118) a translator “must have a source language, text-analytical competence and a corresponding target language text productive competence”. Translators are people who are linguistically and culturally competent in twolanguage, and their work clearly involves putting those two competences together. Farahzad (1992: 276) opines that it is important to examine the level of command of both source and target language, as well as their level of translational competence

Crystal (1987: 344) argues that “for certain types of texts (e.g., scientific material) where translation accuracy is more crucial than naturalness, it makes more sense for the translator to be more fluent in the source language.” Khoury (1998: 92) backs up this claim, and he postulates that the reader of a scientific translation does not seek enjoyment in what he reads. He is rather concerned with understanding the content, which must be rendered accurately with simple expressions as scientific knowledge speaks to the mind and not to feelings or imagination, hence, the importance of grasping the correct source text message and rendering it in clear straightforward language. This is done with help of text analysis.

After analyzing the source text, the translator can be said to be greatly empowered for the process. In some translation cases, proficiency in the target language may not be enough to render a text written in a foreign language. Here the problem lies in the comprehension of the source text. This is another indication that text analysis which facilitates comprehension is of high importance in translation exercise. Such a view is equally stressed by Mackenzie and Vienne (2000: 125), who gives examples of such tasks; (translations of contracts and patents), where the full understanding and accurate rendering of the source text is more important than fluency of the target text.

2.5 Text Analysis and Translation

A survey by Nikitina (2018), showed that text analysis for translation purposes is based on linguistic, cognitive, pragmatic and contextual methods, assisted by computer tools. Nevertheless, analysis for translation purposes is thoroughly specific and relies upon the discursive and intercultural frame of communication, where the translator plays an important mediatory role. Nord (2005) describes the matrix of text analysis as the study of attitude,

status, role, strategy, behavior and activity, which is applicable to the particular communicative situation and the situation of translation,

Nord (2005: 18-19) applies text analysis to the whole of the translation process, since even in the process of creating a translation there is an analytical operation of transcoding. This implies that a translator, after translating will have to do text analysis in order to verify if the source text message was rendered appropriately in the target language. House (2021) notes that the information presented through these discursive categories is modified and displayed differently. The study of all aspects of the text is very important for understanding its pragmatic dimensions to professional experience and didactic situation of translation classes. Meyer (1985:m14) acknowledges that “readers are endowed with different prior knowledge and purposes”. He posits that “A reasonable escape from this problem is to analyze texts from the point of view of the author.” However, Van Dijk, while acknowledging that “differences in knowledge and interests determine discourse comprehension and macrostructure formation”, claims that “there are important methodological reasons to first try to assess the more general, conventional strategies involved in discourse comprehension.” (1977: 30).

This argumentation points to the fact that the proper study of text comprehension (i.e. interpretation), while it has the linguistic descriptions of the text as one of its components, requires the consideration of an unbounded study of phenomena, most of them not defined by the science of linguistics and is therefore not itself a study that belongs solely within linguistic science .

2.6 Previous Studies on Text Analysis in Translation

This debate has given birth to a lot of opinions on the object of the text analysis and what analytical approaches to are adopt in Translation Studies.

Way back in the 80s, Research by Toury (1984: 89) suggests that the production of socially acceptable translation is learnt, not an innate behavior, as we can see from the fact that not all translators achieve it and also from the fact that what is socially acceptable translation changes over time. The behavior is norm governed. Toury again in (1998:1) asserts that “translation requires not only linguistic competence butalso, and perhaps more decisively, cultural competence, both source and target languages, and text analytical competence, which facilitates the translation. Using text analysis to put these factors together

so as to understand why the author of the source text wrote would be a great step to producing quality translations.

Nord (1991) emphasizes the importance of text analysis in achieving effective translation. According to Nord, text analysis involves decoding the underlying structures and meanings of the source text to fully comprehend it before translating it into the target language, Nord argues that translators need to possess strong analytical skills to fully comprehend the source text before attempting its translation. She also identifies three levels of text analysis: micro-level (sentence level), macro-level (text level, and meso-level (discourse level). Her work laid the foundation for subsequent research on text analytical competence, especially that requiring a methodological grounding that would balance out the 'dual loyalty' phenomenon described by Schweitzer in 1998.

Schweitzer (1998), highlighting translators' pursuance of both accuracy (compliance with the original text) and readability (efficient interpretation of the original text). The study showed that they were a number of skills in the lingua-cultural competence for the training of student translators. They are:

- Skill of the compositional accuracy block where the student has the ability to identify linking elements in the source text and find adequate equivalents in the target language.
- Skill of the structural semantic accuracy block where, students have the ability to interpret, cultural semantics of lexical units of the source text and deliver their meaning in the target language.
- Skill of the rhetorical accuracy block, where the student has the ability to recognize communicative strategies used in the source language and ensure accuracy of communicative strategies in the target language.

From the above skills, it is clear that the translation activity starts from the source language. If student translators are not able to interpret elements in the source text accurately, they will encounter problems to accurately represent the source texts elements in the target language.

Conversely, House (2001) returns to the notion of quality. House (2001: 20) examines the relationship between text analysis and translation quality. She confirms that translators with higher text analytical competence are more likely to produce accurate and

faithful translations. House's study highlights the significance of text analysis in ensuring effective translation outcomes. Conversely, the PACTE Group (2003) in their seminal work on the subject, identified text analysis as one of the key components of translation competence. The study provides a deeper understanding of the role of text analytical competence in the overall translation process

Many researchers in the 21st Century have continued to emphasize the role of text analysis in translation. The work by Risku (2010) focuses on the interplay between text analysis and translation process. She argues that effective translation requires translators to analyze the source text at various linguistic levels, including grammar, syntax, and semantics. Risku's work sheds light on the intricate relationship between text analytical competence and translation process. As Angelone (2010) rightly intimates, text analysis plays a crucial role in managing and reducing uncertainties, as translators with higher text analytical competence can better decipher ambiguous or complex source texts. Angelone's study demonstrates the link between text analytical competence and managing uncertainties in translation.

Sakwe (2013: 52-53), using a case study in an African context highlights the impact of being linguistically competent in one's native or 'A' language and in one's foreign or 'B' language on translation performance. His findings proved that language skills and translation skills are symbiotic. This clearly shows that one cannot perform well in translation if the translator is not linguistically competent. Sakwe opines that for a translator to be able to carry out his/her duty, which he describes as "...to unlock the prison of language and help a text break free of its limited original language, culture and audiences", the translator must be able to read and comprehend the source language and write well in the target language. A translator must be able to choose the equivalent expression in the target language that matches the intended meaning in the source language. The study posits that "the key to addressing learners' linguistic needs is by being eclectic rather than being monolithic, and translation can play a role in an integrated way, where all the five skills, namely: reading, writing, listening, speaking and translation are dealt with."

Most recently, Shih (2017: 11) demonstrates through an empirical research that translators with greater text analytical competence are more likely to make informed decisions about translation strategies, resulting in more effective translations. Shih's work contributes to understanding the practical implications of text analytical competence in translation practice, and as Toury suggested way back in Toury (1984:89) "the production of

socially acceptable translations is learnt, not innate behaviour, as we can see that not all translators achieve it and also from the fact that what is socially acceptable translation changes over time.”

3. Methodology

This study is illustrated with a case study survey that makes use an ex-post facto/quasi experiment. Written translations of a protocol test are administered to a purposive sample of 30 final-year students of the Advanced School of Translators and Interpreters (ASTI) of the University of Buea and analyzed for text analytical errors. A text that describes the condition of global economies was selected from a French publication (approximately 300 words) because it posed potential text comprehension problems that can impinge on translation performance. This text has been translated in class in previous years and therefore corresponded to the level of the students.

The study deals with the analysis of the degree of mastery of translational text extrapolations and communicative language errors and mistakes made in the translations from French into English. Suggestions are made in the light of the survey results for textual analytical teaching in translator education. The study adopts a descriptive, semi-experimental, and metanalytic research design. A data analysis Grid is used to analyze the data collected from the translation test. Three data collection methods were used: an opinion survey questionnaire, a structured interview protocol, and a literature review component. The literature review provided empirical data on the principles and practices of textual analytical principles and methods, as well as the nature of its educational dimensions. It drew mostly from peer-reviewed journals, non-peer reviewed journals, and books on textual analysis for translators. The data collection instruments seek to provide answers to the following questions: To what extent does text analytical competence influence the quality of translations? What specific text analytical strategies and methods do translation students use when translating? What pedagogical approaches can be used to develop textual analytical competence in trainee translators? The key descriptive terms used for this research are Translation, Source text, Text analysis, Competence, Effective Translation, curriculum design.

4. Results and Analysis

This section presents survey results on the pertinent issue of text analytical competence in translator education and the major pedagogical implications evoked. Survey instruments of questionnaire and protocol translation text are presented below.

4.1 Questionnaire Data

Table 1. Bio Data of Respondents

S/N	Variable	Details of Question	Description	Frequency	Percentage		
1.	Bio Data of Respondents	Gender	Male	18	35.2		
			Female	32	64.8		
			No response	-	00		
2.		Age		18 - 25	23	46.3	
				26 - 35	20	38.9	
				36 - 45	7	13	
				46 and above	1	1.9	
3.		Education Background		BA in T/I	30	59.3	
				BA in Lang/Lin	30	59.	
				Others	16	31.5	
4.			Occupation/Profession		Teacher	3	5.5
					Translator	11	22.2
	Student				36	72.2	

Gender distribution shows that more females participated in this survey and the survey data also indicates that the majority of respondents fall within the younger age bracket with 46 between 18 and 25. The statistics show a higher proportion of younger individual entering the field. Conversely, the results reveals that a significant portion of respondents (59.3%) holds a bachelor's degree in linguistics, indicating a strong foundation in language related studies among the participants. The remaining 31.5% hold other types of diplomas. This mix highlights the multidisciplinary nature of the translation field and the varied pathways through which individuals enter the profession. Lastly, the survey indicates that the majority of respondents (72.2%) are students. Additionally, 22.2% are professional translators and the remaining 5.5% are teachers. Overall, the distribution of occupations within the survey sample reflects a diverse mix of students, practitioners and educators. These stakeholders are directly concerned with the object of this study.

The next variable solicits information on the familiarity of respondents with the problem identified in this study, which is textual analytical competence.

Table 2. Notion Data of Respondents

S/N	Variable	Details of Question	Description	Frequency	Percentage
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1.	Student's Mastery of Text Analytical Competence	Heard of text analytical competence	Yes	38	76.6
			No	10	20.4
2.	Text Analytical Competence	How will you define textual analytical competence	The ability to understand the overall meaning of a text.	9	18.8
			The ability to analyze the linguistic features of a text.	7	14.6
			The ability to interpret cultural and contextual aspects of a text	5	10.4
			All of the above.	27	53.6
3.		Do you believe that text analytical competence is crucial for effective translation?	Yes, definitely	35	70.4
			Yes, to some extent	11	22.0
			No, not necessarily	1	1.9
			Not sure	3	5.6
4.		On a scale of 1 ton5 rate the importance of text analytical competence in achieving accurate and high-quality translation.	Not important at all	-	-
			Slightly important	1	1.9
			Moderately important	5	9.3
			Very important	26	51.9
			Extremely important	19	37

The data indicates that the majority of students (76.6%) have heard about textual analytical competence while 10 (20.4%) have never heard about it. This awareness is important as textual analytical competence is a valuable skill that can help students critically engage with written material, improve their comprehension and develop their ability to think analytically. The majority of respondents (53.6%) indicated that textual analytical competence involves all of the above aspects: understanding the overall meaning, analyzing linguistic feature and interpreting cultural and contextual aspects of a text. This response reflects a comprehensive understanding of textual analytical competence as a multi-faceted skill that encompasses various dimensions of a text analysis.

Conversely, based on the data provided, 70.4% of the respondents strongly believe that textual analytical competence is crucial in effective translation, while 22% believe that that textual analytical competence is important to some extent. Only 1.9% think that textual analytical competence is not necessary for effective translation. Overall, the data overwhelmingly supports the notion that textual analytical competence is considered crucial. This highlights the importance of developing strong analytical skills to enhance translation

quality, accuracy, and fidelity to original text. Lastly, 51.9% of respondents believe that textual analytical competence is very important in achieving accurate and high-quality translation. 37% state that it is extremely important in achieving accurate and high-quality translation. These responses indicate an even stronger emphasis on the critical role of textual analysis in translation practice.

The next variable investigates the challenges faced by students in reading and analyzing texts during their translation activities.

Table 3. Challenges faced by Students in Textual analysis

S/N	Variable	Details of Question	Description	Frequency	Percentage
1.	Level of Confidence in text analytical competence.	How confident are you in your current mastery of text analytical competence?	Not confident at all	3	5.6
			Slightly confident	7	13
			Moderately confident	30	59.3
			Very confident	11	22
2.		How often do you encounter difficulties in understanding the meaning or context of a text during a translation?	Very often	8	14.8
			Sometimes	32	63
			Always	6	11.1
			Rarely	6	11.1
			Never	00	00
3.		Which elements do you find most challenging to analyze during translation?	Sentence structure and grammar	6	11.1
			Vocabulary and terminology	9	16.7
			Cultural references and idioms	29	57.4
			Tone and Style	8	14.8
4.		Which are the textual elements requiring more attention and analysis?	Sentence structure and grammar	6	11.1
			Vocabulary and terminology	18	35
			Cultural references and idioms	15	29
			Tone and Style	11	5.5

59.3% of the respondents indicated that they are moderately confident in their current level of textual analytical competence. This indicates that a majority of respondents may still have room for improvement or further development. Only 22% of the respondents are very confident and 13% are slightly confident. Some 5.6% of the respondents are not confident at all in their current level of text analytical competence. This group will require

additional support or training to improve their skills and boost their confidence. With regards to difficulties in understanding the meaning or context of a text during translation 63% indicated that they sometimes encounter difficulties. This indicates that to most students understanding the text meaning is not always straightforward but may require additional effort. Conversely 14.8 encounter difficulties very often. This group has consistent challenges and may need to develop strategies to overcome their difficulties. 11.1% always encounter difficulties, while another 11.1% rarely does so and this point to the complexity and nuances involved in understanding text meanings,

The data also indicates that 57.4% of the respondents find cultural references and idioms to be the most challenging textual element to analyze during translation. These elements often carry unique meanings and connotations that may not directly translate into target languages. The translator must possess a deep cultural knowledge and linguistic skills. Conversely, to 16.7% of respondents, vocabulary poses a problem. Translating specialized or domain-specific terminology, nuanced word choices, or abstract concepts can be challenging. On the other hand, 14.1% identified tone and style as most challenging while 11.1% consider sentence structure and grammar as challenging as well. Generally, the data highlights that cultural references and idioms are most challenging text elements inviting translators to navigate a wide range of linguistic, cultural and stylist challenges to ensure accurate and meaningful communication across languages.

Lastly, with regards to textual elements requiring more attention and analysis, the data suggests vocabulary and terminology (35%), and cultural references and idioms (29%). The relatively high percentage of students emphasizing the complexity of cultural references and idioms highlights the critical role of cultural knowledge in successful translation practices. The next section presents the last variable in this study – coping strategies of students.

Table 4. Methods used by students in enhancing Text analytical competence

S/N	Variable	Details of Question	Description	Frequency	Percentage
1.	Coping Strategies of students.	How do you usually enhance your text analytical competence?	Reading extensively in different genres	25	48
			Participating in translation workshops/seminars	25	48.1
			Collaborating with peers to analyze texts together	12	22
			Seeking feedback from experienced translators/editors	12	22

		Others.	-	-
2.	Have you received any formal education in text in analytical training.	Yes	19	35.2
		No	33	64.8
3.	How well do you feel you translation programme/school prepares you in terms of developing text analytical competence	Poorly	2	1
		Somewhat	13	24.1
		Moderately	25	48.1
		Very well	10	20.4
4.	Which are the ways or resources to use of integrating textual analytical competence in training?	It should be included as a course on its own	20	39
		It should be taught from undergraduate to Masters level	14	27
		Dwelling on teaching textual theories	10	19
		Organizing workshops with expert on textual analysis.	5	10
		Equipping trainees with furnished glossaries, dictionaries, encyclopedias and term banks	3	5

The study solicited respondents to indicate the methods used in enhancing text analytical competence. The data reveals that a majority of respondents (45%) do so by reading extensively in several genres. This approach exposes them to a variety of writing styles. Furthermore, some students seek feedback from experience translators (22%) and collaborate with peers to analyze texts (22%). A significant majority of respondents (64.8%) have not received any formal training in textual analysis, while only (34.2%) has done. As to whether their present programs prioritizes textual knowledge, a majority of respondents (48.1%), the school does so only moderately, while 20.4% of respondents say that the program prepares them very well. However, 241%) prepares them somehow in terms of developing text analytical competence.

Lastly, responds were asked to indicate the various ways of improving textual analytical competence in translator' training. Data shows that 39% suggest the introduction of a dedicated course on text analysis, 27% suggest that textual analysis be integrated across all academic programs right from the BA. Some10% solicit that workshops be organized ti enable experts to talk on the subject. Lastly another 5

5 of respondents highlighted the importance of equipping trainees with essential resources like glossaries, dictionaries, encyclopedias and term bases to support their text analysis efforts,

4.2 Text Protocol Data

This section presents the translation results of some eleven pre-selected text analytical competency-linked indicators in 3 tables. The first table presents the French text with model translations provided by this researcher, the second table presents wrong translations of trainees which could then be compared with the models in the first table and finally the third table categorizes the errors according to the chosen models of standard error analysis.

Table 5. Result of pre-selected texts with Text Analytical competence indicators

Text Ref.	Source Text Segments	Researchers Proposed Translations	Text Analytical Elements	Frequency of students' good translations /36	Percentage %
1	Alors que l'économie mondiale continue d'évoluer, les entreprises sont confrontées à de nombreux défis sur un marché de plus en plus compétitif.	As the global economy continues to grow, businesses face numerous challenges in the increasingly competitive marketplace	Context	17	47.2
2	La capacité à s'adapter à ces changements est essentielle pour une croissance et un succès durable.	The ability to adapt to these changes is crucial for sustainable growth and success	Terminology, cultural nuances, vocabulary, tone	14	38.8
3	Il n'est pas toujours facile de naviguer dans le paysage économique complexe.	However, it is not always easy to navigate the complex economic landscape.	Terminology and vocabulary	11	30.5
4	L'un des facteurs les plus importants qui influencent les décisions commerciales est les fluctuations des taux de change des devises.	One of the most significant factors influencing business decisions is fluctuations in currency exchange rates	Terminology and vocabulary	16	44.4
5	Ces fluctuations peuvent influencer les entreprises importatrices et exportatrices, en modifiant le coût et la rentabilité des biens et services.	These fluctuations can impact both import and export businesses, altering the cost and profitability of goods and services.	Terminology, grammar and vocabulary	11	30.5
6	Comprendre les implications des fluctuations des devises et prédire avec précision leurs tendances futures est essentiel pour que les entreprises prennent des	Understanding the implications of currency fluctuations and accurately predicting their future trends is essential for businesses to make informed decisions.	Idiomatic expressions	18	50

	décisions éclairées.				
7	L'économie repose sur le principe de l'équilibre entre l'offre et la demande pour déterminer les prix et l'équilibre du marché.	Economics is built upon the principle of balancing supply and demand to determine prices and market equilibrium	Terminology, cultural nuances and vocabulary	13	36.1
8	Cet équilibre délicat peut être perturbé par divers facteurs tels que les changements dans les préférences des consommateurs, les avancées technologiques ou les événements mondiaux	This delicate balance can be disrupted by various factors such as changes in consumer preferences, technological advancements or global events.	grammar	12	33.3
9	Les traducteurs doivent être conscients du contexte économique et transmettre avec précision ces concepts économiques pour assurer une communication claire entre les entreprises et leurs marchés cibles	Translators must be cognizant of the economic context and accurately convey these economic concepts to ensure clear communication between businesses and their target markets	Audience and grammar	19	52.7
10	De plus, les politiques économiques et les réglementations jouent un rôle important dans la formation de l'environnement commercial.	Furthermore, economic policies and regulations play a significant role in shaping the business environment.	Cultural nuances, vocabulary, and context	13	36.1
11	Les gouvernements mettent en œuvre différentes mesures pour réguler les industries, promouvoir une concurrence équitable et gérer la stabilité économique.	Governments implement various measures to regulate industries, promote fair competition and manage economic stability.	Context	19	62.7

The data presented on this table indicate that students struggle with various aspects of textual analytical competence. These include Mastery of context with only (47.2%) of students having an understand of context. Other elements include terminology and vocabulary, only 44.4%) of respondents have a good grasp of terminology and vocabulary used in the text. Poor mastery of cultural references and nuances comes next. The low percentage of students who have mastered these aspects suggest that there is need for more focus on cultural context in textual analysis. Lastly, Idiomatic expressions register only 47%. Overall, the data highlight areas where students may need additional support and instruction to improve textual competence. The next table presents results of inappropriate translation of students.

Table 6. Students Inappropriate Translations

Text Ref.	Source Text Segments	Researchers Proposed Translations	Text Analytical Elements	Frequency of students' erroneous translations /36	Percentage %
1	Alors que l'économie mondiale continue d'évoluer, les entreprises sont confrontées a de nombreux défis sur un marche de plus en plus compétitif.	As the global economy continues <i>to go high</i> <i>The world economy is growing...</i>	Context	19	52.7
2	La capacite à s'adapter à ces changements est essentielle pour une croissance et un succès durable.	The ability to adapt to these changes is essential for <i>long-lasting</i> growth and success <i>...durable growth</i> Adapt to <i>those...</i> changes..	Terminology, cultural nuances, vocabulary, tone	22	61.2
3	Il n'est pas toujours facile de naviguer dans le paysage économique complexe.	It is not always easy to navigate <i>through these</i> complex economic landscape. ... It is not always easy to <i>partake in complex economic activities</i>	Terminology and vocabulary	19	52.7
4	L'un des facteurs les plus importants qui influencent les décisions commerciales est les fluctuations des taux de change des devises.	<i>One of the factors governing business decisions is the fluctuations of currencies' exchange</i> <i>...one of the most important factors thst influence</i> <i>....commercial decisions is the fluctuation of exchange rate of devices</i>	Terminology and vocabulary	20	55.5
5	Ces fluctuations peuvent influencer les entreprises importatrices et exportatrices, en modifiant le cout et la rentabilité des biens et services.	<i>This fluctuation can influence both on importing and exporting companies.</i> <i>...This fluctuation can also influence ..</i>	Terminology, grammar and vocabulary	23	63.8
6	Comprendre les implications des fluctuations des devises et prédire avec précision leurs tendances futures est essentiel pour que les entreprises prennent des décisions éclairées.	Understanding the implications of currency fluctuations and accurately predicting <i>their future tendencies</i> is essential for businesses <i>to take clear decisions.</i> <i>....currency exchange entails and predict its future effects</i> <i>...understanding devices</i> <i>...Future tendencies</i> is essential for economies	Idiomatic expressions terminology	18	50
7	L'économie repose sur le principe de l'équilibre entre l'offre et la	Economics <i>relies</i> upon the principle of <i>balannce</i> supply and	Terminology, cultural nuances and	23	63.8

	demande pour déterminer les prix et l'équilibre du marché.	demand to ...Economy lays on the principle of the	vocabulary		
8	Cet équilibre délicat peut être perturbé par divers facteurs tels que les changements dans les préférences des consommateurs, les avancées technologiques ou les événements mondiaux	This delicate balance can be disrupted by various factors such as changes in consumer preferences, technological processes or global events. In the consumer preferences ... technological advances	Grammar terminology	24	66.6
9	Les traducteurs doivent être conscients du contexte économique et transmettre avec précision ces concepts économiques pour assurer une communication claire entre les entreprises et leurs marchés cibles	Translators must be recognize of the economic context and accurately translate those economic concepts to ensure clear communication between businesses and their target markets	Audience and grammar	19	52.7
10	De plus, les politiques économiques et les réglementations jouent un rôle important dans la formation de l'environnement commercial.	Furthermore, economic policies and rules play a Significant role in the creation of the business environment.in the training of trade environment ... in the formation of business environment ...development of the commercial environment ... In the establishing of ... In the building an economic environment	Cultural nuances, vocabulary, and context	13	36.1
11	Les gouvernements mettent en œuvre différentes mesures pour réguler les industries, promouvoir une concurrence équitable et gérer la stabilité économique.	Governments apply various measures to organize industries, promote equal competition and manage economic stability.	Context	17	47.7

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The data presented on table 6 indicate that students are struggling significantly with various elements of textual analysis, as evidenced in the high frequency of errors committed in each area. More than half of the students (52.7%) made errors related to understanding and applying context in textual analysis is concerned. This means that students missed key information that could impact their comprehension and analysis of text. Conversely the 63.8% of terminology and vocabulary related errors point to the significant challenge these

constitute to students. This situation is similar to that of idiomatic expressions where up to 52.7% of errors are commuted. Even grammatical errors record a 52.7% frequency. Overall, the data paints of students battling with elements of textual analysis. The high frequency of errors in context, terminology and vocabulary, Idiomatic expressions and grammar, underscores the need for target support and instruction to help students improve their skills in analysis and interpreting texts effectively.

5. Discussions of the Results

The results of the protocol test show that most of the students encountered difficulties in translating lingo-stylistic, and socio-pragmatic elements of economic text. Most mistranslation are due to difficulties in understanding the meaning of some words of the SL text which caused them to fail to translate appropriately from the point view of the TL readers. Other mistranslations occurred due to unfamiliarity with economic concepts, terminology and idiomatic expressions which lead to difficulties in choosing the proper expression in the target language. Furthermore, lack of cultural awareness of economic discourse, profuse lack of knowledge of the grammar of both languages and carelessness lead to inappropriate translation. Hence, students found difficulties in choosing the appropriate equivalence in translation.

Since any translation activity necessarily focuses on "texts" of two languages, it is very important for the translation students to know the features of these 'texts.' Text features are generally divided into two categories, "form" and "function" features. The "form" features include the grammatical, lexical and syntactic structure of the text, whereas "function" features refer to purposes of designing those linguistic forms. It is very useful if the students of translation are trained on how to do text analytical activities before, they start translation exercises. As Liu Zequan (2003) rightly points out, these analyses are not just interested in what language is, but why language is; not just what language means, but how language means. This classroom procedure is expected to complement a systematic teaching of reading, language and culture. and should reflect the purposeful, task-based, interactive nature: contrastive and functional grammar, comprehension and text analytical skills, terminology and intercultural semantics, translator-specific writing tasks, and language technology tools for Translation. This researcher objects to the view that language skills and translation skills can be treated as two independent variables: "first learn the language, then learn to translate" (Titford and Hieke, 1985: 26). Kiraly (1995: 34) states that communicative

approach to second language teaching has important implications for translation training. Then, he adds that “new ideas in translation classrooms include using methods such as roleplay and simulation that create a greater sense of realism - and thereby generate enthusiasm and overcome passivity, teach translation as a realistic communicative activity” (Kiraly, 1995: 33). Such applied translation classes offer students the opportunity to develop their translation skills through practice, i.e., through interactive class work complemented by textual analysis and language study. It will be necessary to understand what teachers must know and do to improve student learning. Most importantly, a model of learning that informs all the opportunities provided for teachers to engage in the improvement of students’ skills over time will be needed.

5.1 Proposal for A Model of Translator’s Text Analytical Competence from an Educational Perspective

This study postulates that an increased institutional support through language enhancement be El-Sheikh (1987: 121) given to cater for the trainee translators’ profile gaps. The key to addressing learners’ linguistic needs is by being eclectic rather than being monolithic, and translation can play a role in an integrated way, where all the five skills, namely, reading, writing, listening, speaking, and translation, are dealt with. suggests a communicative approach to the teaching of translation that might help the students to develop their language skills systematically. He opines that “Since the students are at the same time improving their language skills, we often use source texts and authentic translations on the basis of which we comment on the translation strategies applied and their effectiveness in view of the (assumed) purpose.”

There have been no major reforms to address the generalized disequilibrium existing between the students diversity conundrums and the teaching practices as one would expect in translation classroom. One cause of disillusionment is the lack of responsive trainers whose duty it is to identify the gaps in students’ profile and apply studied ideas and methods. Many untrained teachers would find these guidelines rather too superficial. This study recommends that the training of trainers be intensified and more seminars organized for heads of department, who will, in turn, pass on the new methods to their colleagues in their respective departments.

Conversely, in a bid to impart essential translation skills to students and enable them to acquire linguistic, discursive, analytical and cultural competence within the framework of

developing their sense of analysis and synthesis, of creativity and judgement, this study recommends the use of valuable authentic materials for translation practice: exercises textual analysis, exercises on language enrichment, exercises on cultural enrichment, and exercises in personal involvement. In this vein, the following pedagogical approaches and activities are indispensable: inaugural activities made up of orientation and warm-up sessions before translation begins; text analysis made up of exercises that elicit students' familiarity with the text's structure, form and function; snowball activities involving progressive activities like group work, team competition, language worksheets, oral activities; feedback activities which create a forum for exchange of experiences and studied ideas between teachers and students, as well as among students themselves; workshop sessions which provide a forum for discussion and examination of practical issues in translating; and research/field work sessions which provide a forum for extracting information and terminology from real communicative settings.

These activities would activate and maintain interest and involvement by using a variety of student-centered activities to supplement the source text as a language laboratory, to facilitate the tapping of knowledge resources and group experience, to help students to explore their own responses to translation, to prompt the frequent use of the target language, and to integrate language and translation in a mutually inclusive manner. According to Schiffrin, (1994) there are three key issues to text or discourse analysis: "the relationship between structure and function, the relationship between text and context, and the nature of communication" (p. 18)

Discourse as "language in use" is crucial in translation teaching and provides a solid ground for teaching context analysis as the study of "how stretches of language, considered in their full textual, social, and psychological context, become meaningful and unified for their users" (1989: ix). From an increase in language awareness within the parameters of form and function, learners are encouraged to look at language as a system and to examine what language does in the given context. As (Carter, 2003:64) points out, the shift from a schemata-view to a language-awareness-view is an apt one in terms of pedagogy. Thus, language awareness, being defined as "the development in learners of an enhanced consciousness and sensitivity to the forms and functions of language" is seen as an ability, while schemata, described as "the previously acquired knowledge structures" (Carrell and Eisterhold, 1983: 556), are seen as factual information.

6. Conclusion

It is apparent that to teach linguistic and translation textual analysis is methodologically justified and valuable. As the analysis of the data suggests, the developed instructional framework, which is rooted in various discourse models is applicable. In this pragmatic model any translation student should know that there are some skills s/he should master. S/he must be highly proficient in two or more working languages; must have a broad knowledge of general culture and specific and detailed knowledge of his or her specialized field. Above all the translator must be a good writer and reader as well. Ideally, possessing these qualities should be enough to be able to translate a wide variety of texts and to produce quality translations.

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